

Crop Yield Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract:

Agriculture is the one which gave birth to cultivation. Crop productivity is one of the major sources of Indian Economy. The useful and correct information about the new technologies should be provided to improve crop yield rate which plays a major role in farming. The very important factor in the agriculture planning is crop selection. Different parameters such as market price, production rate and the different government policies will influence the selection of crops. Indian economy will be improved by improving agriculture which should undergo many changes. By using machine learning techniques, we can improve agriculture which is applied easily on farming sector. The concept of this paper is to implement crop selection method and to focus on few applications of machine learning techniques which will help in maximizing the rate of crop yield and in turn improves our Indian Economy.

Keywords: Crop Productivity, Market price, Production rate, Machine Learning

Introduction:

The essential issue in agricultural industry is to predict the crop production. Achieving maximum production of crop yield rate with limited number of resources is the main objective of agricultural planning. Many machine learning algorithms can help in improving the production of crop yield rate. Whenever there is loss in unfavourable conditions, we can apply crop selection method and reduce the losses. And it may be helpful in gaining crop yield rate in favourable conditions which in turn helps in improving India's economy. We have some of the factors that influence the crop yield rate. They are seed quality and crop selection. We need to test the quality of the seeds before sowing. Selection of crops depends on favourable and unfavourable conditions which can be improved by using hybridization methods. Machine learning techniques can be used to improve crop production. Some of the geographical conditions of the region like river ground, hill areas or the depth areas help in crop production. Weather conditions like humidity, rainfall, temperature, cloud are also helpful in crop production. Different predictions can be made by implementing different techniques for different crops. These predictions are categorized into two type's namely traditional statistic method and

Received: 22 January 2024

Revised: 2 February 2024

Final Accepted 15 February 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10663122>

machine learning techniques. For predicting single sample spaces traditional statistic method can be used. And for predicting multiple sample spaces machine learning methods can be used.

Literature Review:

Applications of Machine Learning Techniques in Agricultural Crop Production by Subhadra Mishra, Debahuti Mishra and Gour Hari Santra suggested that the integration of computer science with agriculture helps in forecasting agricultural crops. This method also helps in providing information of crops and how to increase yield rate. The algorithms such as Artificial Neural networks, Decision Tree Algorithms are used to predict the agricultural crops [1]

Applications in Indian Agriculture using Machine Learning by Karandeep Kaur has provided an insight into the troubles faced by our Indian farmers and how these can be solved using various techniques. This method helps in increasing the farming sector in the countries and apply the more machine learning applications [2]

Crop Selection Method Based on Various Environmental Factors Using Machine Learning by Nishit Jain, Amit Kumar, Sahil Garud, Vishal Pradhan, Prajakta Kulkarni helped in Predicting crop sequences and maximizing yield rates and making benefits to the farmers. Predicting crop diseases, studying crop simulations are also done with machine learning applications [3].

PROPOSED WORK

Two different methods are to be considered for selecting the crop and the methods are

1. Crop Selection method
 2. Crop sequencing method
- 1) CROP SELECTION METHOD

Crop selection method means selecting crop(s) based on various environmental and economic factors like soil type, average temperature, market prices etc. The selection of crop can be done by many machine learning algorithms. The different crop diseases and defects or change in properties are noticed on using different soil types.

Crop Prediction Algorithm:

Step 1: Consider different crop datasets.

Step 2: Data cleaning process should be done to remove some attributes which are no required and ignore the datasets with missing values.

Step 3: Apply decision tree classifier to train the models in the dataset which is explained below.

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Step 4: Consider various factors such as temperature, humidity, type of soil, estimated rainfall for crop prediction.

Step 5: Add the above mentioned factors at the end of the list along with different datasets.

Step 6: The decision tree algorithm will predict the best suited crop based on the list of datasets or crops given.

2) CROP SEQUENCING METHOD

Based on the yield rate and market prices crop sequencing algorithm is used in selection of crops. The yield and prices may change according to the climate and market conditions. The Crop Sequencing algorithm suggests the suitable set of crops to be grown over the full season time.

The crop sequencing algorithm works on the basis of predicted yield rate as well as the market prices. This helps us to base our predictions not only on the yield rate but also the market prices

Applications of Machine Learning Techniques in Crop Prediction:

1) Decision Tree:

Decision Tree is a technique that can be used for Classification problems. The concepts such as nodes, branches, terminal values, payoff values are included in the decision tree model. The model is a tree-structured representation, where internal nodes depict the features of a dataset, branches depict the decision rules and each leaf node represents the outcome. A Decision tree , consists of two nodes namely Decision Node and Leaf Node. Decision nodes are used to make any decision and have multiple branches, whereas Leaf nodes are the output of those decisions and do not contain any further branches. It is a graphical representation used for making a decision based on given conditions. There are two step processes for the construction of a decision tree algorithm- first, growth of large decision tree then reduction of size and over fitting the data, in the second step, and tree is pruned. The pruned decision tree that is used for classification purposes is called the classification tree.

2) Regression Analysis:

Regression analysis is a statistical method that shows the relation between two or more variables. Regression Analysis is used in weather forecasting and crop yield prediction. This analysis is used by agricultural scientists to identify the effect of different fertilizers and how it affects the yield of the crops. For example, the analysts might use different types of fertilizers and water on fields to understand if there is an impact on the crop's yield. The analysts will change the number of fertilizers and water to maximize the crop output based on the result.

3. Clustering:

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Revised: 2 February 2024

Final Accepted 15 February 2024

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Clustering means the arrangement of a set of objects such that the objects in the same group are similar to each other when compared to the objects in any other group. It is a repetitive process of information discovery that requires domain expertise and human judgment used frequently to make adjustments to the data and the model parameters to achieve the desired result. Clustering is used in many fields such as machine learning, retail business, disease management, image segmentation, information retrieval, and agriculture etc. There are various clustering algorithms are there such as k-means, mean shift, **Density-Based Spatial Clustering**, Hierarchical clustering but the common and important clustering algorithm is k-means which is mainly used for crop prediction based on weather forecast.

Experimental Result:

From the above proposed work and algorithm, the expected result is given as follows.

Type of Soil	PH Value	Estimated Rainfall (mm)	Temperature (c)	Suitable Crop	Estimated Crop Rate
Black	7.0	829	30	Cotton	60%
Black	7.3	720	29	Green Gram	90%
Alluvial	6.5	885	27	Rice`	85%
Red	7.2	570	28	Castor	65%

Conclusion:

Agriculture is the field which helps in economical growth of our country. Hence our farmers should know all the new technologies of machines learning and other new techniques. These techniques of machines learning are applied on agriculture to improve yield of crops. Sensor technologies are implemented in many farming sectors. This paper helps in selecting proper crop for their selected land and selected season. These techniques will solve the problems of farmers in agriculture field. This will help in improving the economic growth of our country.

Future enhancement:

- Quantify recommendation for varieties: Currently the direction in which the factors affect yield is available. I would like to quantify this effect and hopefully give more precise recommendations
- Incorporate more weather variables: Temperature, humidity, hours of sunlight.
- Incorporate soil data.
- Attempt to use mixed models (treating some predicators as random variables)

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